

ETHICS AND AESTHETICS IN THE FORM OF SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL METHODS OF DEVELOPING SKILLS IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES AND TEACHER INFLUENCE

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Abstract: this article provides insights into the methods of determining the abilities of young people who are the future of society and the abilities that every future pedagogue should acquire. The educational process is facilitated by the joint cooperation of the teacher and the student. That is why, in order to improve the quality of education, paying attention to the teacher's potential and the student's knowledge and skills was comprehensively covered.

Keywords: students, abilities, teacher's personality, lesson structure, ethics and aesthetics of teacher's behavior, knowledge and skills, teacher's pedagogical skills

Every country building its spiritual life and future appeals to moral values such as national goodness, humanity, honesty, selflessness, nobility, kindness, conscientiousness, and justice. These qualities are formed in society, community and family environment. A number of aspects and characteristics are embodied in human spirituality: human qualities such as modesty and concern, loyalty and loyalty, diligence and generosity, kindness and compassion, conscience and sincerity, learning and intelligence, gentleness and humility are the moral basis of spirituality.

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Teaching is a great art. A pedagogue cannot easily achieve this art by himself. The famous pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius states that "Teaching is a very proud profession, higher than any other profession on earth." These words are not spoken in vain. A teacher is compared to a burning candle. It radiates light everywhere. When describing the image of a teacher, we repeat that his personality should have the following qualities: conscientious, hardworking, consistent, moral, loving his work, treating students sweetly, instilling in them a desire for knowledge, making students learn. A person who follows z and has his own beliefs.

he worldview of every pedagogue is reflected in his behavior. Language is the main tool of communication. Therefore, it is appropriate for the educator to be very careful in the process of dealing with it. "Education needs three things: talent, knowledge and practice," said the great scholar Aristotle. So, a teacher is a professional image of a person with a complex personality structure, who takes a leading place in the life of society. His work is the basis of achievements in all spheres of social life. Pedagogical-psychological preparation and integration of knowledge, behavior culture, consideration of psychological situations should be strong. Only high-level, highly skilled teachers can educate a well-rounded person of the people's dreams. First of all, the teacher develops knowledge, skills and competence. The teacher also teaches feelings of love for the country and belief in values. Teaching is a difficult and responsible profession. Teachers are not bad. In any educational institution, we meet many teachers and learn. Their appearances, teaching methods, and spirituality are also different. In the process of education, students pay close attention to the teacher. His appearance and behavior should be

as refined as this profession. During the teacher's educational activities, the child's adaptation to the environment creates the basis for ensuring the need for mental growth and personal development. As a result of this activity, the student acquires new knowledge, skills and competences. The success of the educational process also depends on the teaching principle of the teacher. In this place, our grandfather Alisher Navoi, a great thinker, said: "Even if a disciple achieves kingship, it is better if he serves his teacher." In fact, the teacher educates the student so that he can master any field and become a mature staff of any profession. Today's young people are very attentive and demanding. A teacher must know everything. The word "I don't know" should be memorized. Because during the lesson, the student asks the teacher for an answer to an unknown question. If the teacher has a high level and deep knowledge, he can answer. Then he will be respected by the students. What if he can't answer? He is respected in front of the students. A teacher can subjugate and follow students only with deep knowledge. Pedagogical skills that a teacher should know:

- Didactic ability
 - Academic ability
 - Perceptive ability
 - Communication skills
 - Speech ability
 - Organizational ability
 - Gnostic ability...
- Didactic ability is a way to adapt and deliver difficult educational material to students by making it easier, more complex, simpler, and more understandable.
- Academic ability is the teacher's ability to have deep and broad knowledge of the subject taught by him, as well as other subjects. This ability is very useful for the teacher. Especially elementary school students go beyond the scope of the lesson and look for answers to their unanswered questions.

- Perceptive ability is a teacher's ability to be psychologically observant, taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of the student.

- Communicative ability is the ability to communicate with children and find the right way to interact with students.

- In order to successfully implement interpersonal discipline and cultural behavior education with students, the teacher should not use the methods of external influence of the teacher, but the goals of the system of needs and motives related to the student's critical activity and the limit of development. it is necessary to cooperate with students based on development methods.

- Speech ability is the teacher's ability to clearly and clearly express his feelings with the help of speech, at the same time with the help of mime and pantomime. During the lesson, a talented teacher can attract students to the lesson with his speech. In the lesson, the speech of a talented teacher is always aimed at students. Whether the teacher explains a new topic, explains the student's question or reprimands, conducts educational lessons, whatever he does, his speech always has an internal quality, such as his reliability and attractiveness. should be distinguished by power. The teacher's speech and pronunciation should be clear, simple, and understandable for students. According to A. Djersild's research, what kind of teachers do children prefer?

They love and respect a teacher who is kind, honest, cheerful, hard-working, free-spirited, and respectful of others. Because the lesson of a teacher with such a character will not be boring. Students can freely express their opinions, be it wrong or right.

- Organizational ability is the ability to organize the teaching process and extracurricular activities, to organize and unite a group of students. A teacher's ability to organize his work means that he can properly plan and control his work. Experienced teachers develop a special sensitivity to time - the ability to properly distribute work and use the intended time.

- Gnostic ability refers to the teacher's ability to use and apply existing knowledge. A knowledgeable and experienced teacher draws the structure of the lesson using his knowledge during the lesson. He shares and shares his knowledge with the students during the lesson.

Long-term research has shown that pedagogical skills consist of complex and multifaceted psychological knowledge. We have highlighted several components of pedagogical skills above. It should be noted that the ability of a person is related to his inclinations and interests, and the interrelationship of skills, knowledge, and skills. Diagnosing students' ability, individual approach to finding the content of ability is also effective for the quality of education. The role of the teacher in developing such abilities in students is incomparable. A teacher should be a role model for students in every aspect. Because the representative of education for a child is the parent, and the representative of education is the teacher. We see many different teachers in any educational institution. But we cannot say that all of them are cultured and spiritual, embodying all abilities. When the teacher is teaching, the student observes him in every way. Therefore, we cannot say that all teachers can be role models. But there are such teachers that every word that comes out of their mouth is knowledge. Every student who sees their behavior culture, dress culture and nobility, intends to be such a person in the future. tries to be. In our people, one hour of class is equal to one day of prayer. Whatever success and results we have achieved in life, we always acknowledge with gratitude that you have an inestimable contribution to these achievements. We all know that our great poet, Maulana Furqat, described knowledge as "the music of the soul, the light of the seeing eyes."

In fact, it is worthwhile to express all our praises to our hardworking and noble teachers who inculcate the knowledge of science in the hearts of millions of young people and raise them to become people worthy of the country.

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